

A conceptual study on Evaluating corporate social Responsibility of Anand Milk Union Limited (Amul)

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ABSTRACT

The world is moving at an enormous speed. Every country wants to be a superpower nation. The countries are encouraging the corporate sector to develop the overall aspects of the country. It may be the improvement of infrastructure, Education, a Sustainable environment, as well as the economic growth and Gross Domestic Product of the nation. The Corporate Social Responsibility Policy is a key element of a company, which will work on the well-being of the customer, society, and all other stakeholders. Each corporate house has been adopted a strategy of CSR policy to expand their business and long sustainability. Before giving any preference to the company the customer thinks about what the particular company provides him and to society and how the particular company takes care of him. In this matter our paper trying to analyze the effects of CSR policy followed by Amul. The study was based on the existing research studies and secondary data from various sources.

Keywords: Company, Customer, Corporate.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Business and society have a mutual relationship with each other. The relationship between business and society is important for the success of every business. Both are interdependent. If a business acts honestly towards society as a return society will contribute more for rising profits if business. To maintain a long-term relationship with society, and its stakeholder they following corporate social responsibility. LordHolmes and Richard Walts (2010) have defined “Corporate Social Responsibility as the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families as well as the local community and society at large”. Corporate social responsibility is a trustable business activity of a company that is based on ethical values, compliance with legal requirements, and respect for people, communities, and their environment. It is a business tactic used by the firm that brings a sustainable environment by delivering economic, social, and environmental benefits for all stakeholders. The stakeholder is maybe individuals, or groups having interests, rights, or ownership in an organization and its activities. They expect more from the company. They expect, the company should be accountable and transparent. The employees are the important capital to any business as a member of stakeholder, they expect a good workplace, effective wage, and salary, career planning, and development, equal opportunities, hospitality, etc. Then customers are the real boss of the company, the customer decision will play a major role in the growth of the company. They have the capacity to winding the company and fire any employee. However, a customer is also an important stakeholder, they anticipate the good quality of product and services, at a reasonable price, safety, and ethical advertising, etc. following investors expect a fair return for the investment, security of funds, government expect timely payment of tax, timely disclosure, etc. The competitors expect fair and healthy competition. These have become more responsible for the company. The company has to besocially responsible at any time and at any cost, it will bring more fruits and good status to the organization. In this matter, Corporate Social Responsibility has become an important approach to the company.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Henri Servaes and Ane Tamayo (July 2012): Their study found that the firms engaging in and publicizing CSR activities can only add value if these activities and firm reputation are aligned. So, a firm with has poor reputations are unlikely to reap immediate benefits from engaging in CSR. In long run, the engagement in and dissemination of such activities could create value if they change the customer's perceptions of the firm.

Jeremy Galbreath: the study examined that the firm that demonstrates compliance with law or offers outstanding care for employees or communities maybe in the best position to diminish employee loss. On the other hand, the economic, legal, and discretionary dimensions of CSR were positively associated with customer satisfaction.

Dd. Dipl (2012): He found that CSR performance can be measured. He says that it is necessary to measure changes in stakeholder's satisfaction levels due to investment in CSR. CSR should be integrated into education, training, and research with potential funding possibilities.

ReenaShyam (May 2016): paper examined that there is a need for the creation of awareness about CSR amongst the general public to make CSR initiatives more effective.

3.OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

Corporate social responsibility is vitally essential to long-term business success.

1. To study the concept of corporate social responsibility.
2. To understand the CSR initiative practiced by Amul Company.

4.METHODOLOGY:

This study consists application of secondary data. Information about corporate social responsibility and its relevance for the development and growth of the economy and the society are outlined using the findings and outcomes of the existing research articles and reports in research articles and annual reports.

5.SCOPE OF STUDY:

This study helps to understand the significance of CSR initiatives for social welfare. This study also benefits society and industries to have better insights on possible future prospects for the betterment of social conditions by contributing totheenvironment and enhancing economic conditions.

Company Profile:

Amul is an Indian dairy cooperative based in the state of Gujarath. It was founded in the year 1946 by TribhuvandasPatel. At present, the revenue of the company is 5.9 billion dollars. It has employed more than 3.6 million milk producers. Amul is famous for its white revolution.

Corporate Social Responsibility of Amul:

Amul is one of the most reputed and high emerging companies in India, having the slogan of The Taste of India, it began its business with two village cooperatives and 250 liters of milk per day. Amul inspired the 'operational Flood' and heralded the 'white Revolution' in India. Amul is recognized as the country's largest milk-producing cooperative and hasareputation all over the country. The success of Amul shows its unique CSR policy.

Tribhuvandas Foundation

The Tribhuvandas foundation is one of the rural health and development programs of Amul. This program was inspired by the Shri TribhuvandasPatel, founder chairman of Amul. TribuvandasPatel was the founder of the Kaira district cooperative milk producers' union in 1946. He felt that there is a need for medical health services to serve farmers out of sickness. For this matter,Patel started tribuvandas foundation in Kaira village. Tribhuvandas pate awarded Ramon Magsaysay Award for community leadership. He donated prize money of awards and funds he received from Kaira farmers on his retirement, for lifetime service to them to set up this foundation. Dr. V. Kurien also played an active role in this setup. It was registered as a charitable trust under the public trust act 1950, in July 1975.The foundation has a unique future and it is a need-based program for villages and it is operating by the village people themselves. It is started to work for full filling

the needs of the village. It has headquartered at Anand with its sub-centers spread over the district Anand and Kheda. The foundation has an enthusiastic team of a medical officers, nurses, administrative staff, and they provide the following services: Treatment of common ailments, immunization through vaccination-BCG, Triple Vaccine, Polio, measles, Tetanus, Anti rabies at subsidized rate, treatment of tuberculosis and anemia, Antenatal, postnatal care, neonatal and infant care, Nutritional rehabilitation centers for undernourished children and vulnerable mothers, identification of suspected cases of cancer and building contact with the government for family planning program in rural areas, cancer awareness program, detection camp and treatment at Shri Krishna Hospital, Karam said, Karamsasad Balwadis (Daycare centers) for pre-school play and learning activities for children of three to five years. This foundation also providing continuous training and retraining to the workers, who are chosen from a village with help of the dairy co-operative societies. It enables the workers to provide primary health care and health education from door to door in groups and at the dairy co-operative society's centers with confidence. This foundation has implemented a concept of "Safe Delivery Kid" in India ensuring safe and clean delivery of a pregnant mother. This program has a partnership with the government, to spread services to the whole state. The foundation has achieved a drastic reduction in the percentage of low birth weight in the Anand and Kheda district. The foundation is the recipient of the first prize for the best effort in family welfare in the voluntary sector from the ministry of health and family welfare government of India in 1993.

Swarna Jayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana

It is a self-employment program practiced by Amul. The basic objective of this program is to bring below the poverty line families below the poverty line by providing them assets to become self-employed.

6. TREE PLANTATION:

Protecting the environment is a prime duty of every person. So Amul started the CSR of tree plantation in the year 2007 with a lot of dedication to protecting the environment. Its main aim is to plant the trees and make India a country called Green India thereby, it can reduce the effect of global warming. For the past nine years with the help of Gujarat dairy co-operatives, they are conducting a tree plantation program on Independence Day. Their main motto is one member one tree. More than nineteen lakh trees will be grown on Independence Day every year. Not only growing that but also taking proper care of it every day. By this, they have made an oath to protect the environment. They also conduct awareness and training programs among the people in most of the villages of Gujarat about the benefits and needs of nature. In most the cases people die only because of the reason that no proper available of blood when it is necessary. In order to eliminate this problem, Amul has made an attempt to save the valuable life of the people by the blood donation camp. Humanity to peace is an intention behind it. It was started from the year 1987. It is being organized in rural areas in amul village dairy co-operative society. Amul dairy Employees, members with their family members take part in blood donation camp. They also made an attempt to donate blood in case of emergency. With the help of this it has saved more than thousands of lives of people.

7. RURAL SANITATION CAMPAIGN:

Making India clean is one of the aim of Amul in that case amul is providing loan facility to construct toilets. It is providing interest free loan to milk producers to construct toilets. They have constructed many toilets in anand and kheda districts of Gujarat. Amul have jointly partnered members of District Rural Development Agency (DRDA) for taking this initiative. For constructing one toilet it cost around 11,500 rupees. DRDA will provide 4,600 be rupees and remaining amount will be provided by amul company. If members or employees of amul want to construct toilet then it will provide interest free loan which should be returnable within four years.

8. AMUL SCHOLARSHIPS:

Amul always want to take care of their workers, besides this they also encourage the children of farmers in pursuing the education. So, they have started this programme from the year 1992. They provide regular scholarship to the children of farmers.

9.AMUL SCHOLARSHIP FELICITATION PROGRAMME:

Under this programme every outstanding student will be selected from village who score highest marks in class tenth and twelfth. Amul will provide free higher education to those students. Also, gold medal list students will be selected from degree and free accommodation and education will be provided to those students. Amul also help those students to get seat in IIT's and IIM's. Amul has helped poor students to fulfill their dreams.

10.AMUL VIDYA SHREE AND VIDYA BHUSHAN:

Besides providing free higher education to those students it also awards those students. Merit students from class tenth, twelfth, degree, P.G will be awarded this award. Their vision is that educated and talented youth students will contribute to the nation building so those students should be recognized and should be provided with necessary requirements which will help those students. They have given award to more than twenty thousand students across India.

11.OBSERVATIONS:

1. It is found that Corporate social responsibility will influence on the business to adopt ethical values and to extend respect towards the people and community.
2. It is understood that corporate social responsibility ensures sustainable environment by delivering economic, social benefit for all stakeholders.
3. Corporate social responsibility also ensures fair and healthy competition in the market.
4. The study also reveals that it helps the organization to build positive customer perception towards the firm.
5. It is found that corporate social responsibility initiatives help the organization in enhancing stakeholder satisfaction.
6. It is also observed that corporate social responsibility of amul inspired by providing medical health services through Tribhuvandas foundation.
7. The study also reveals that Amul has initiated for the Tree plantation drive in the year 2007 to create Green India.
8. It is also observed that Amul started Holistic campaign called blood donation to serve humanity by providing necessary required blood in emergency.

12.SUGGESTIONS:

From the above study we came to know that Amul is highly contributing to the education sector and rural development of India as a CSR. Farmers are the main stake holders of Amul, in that matter Amul contribute to the farmers and receive the same return from them. So, every business should prominently contribute to the stakeholders of the firm as Corporate social responsibility than contributing to other sector. Maintaining good relation with stakeholders is mandatory than earning profit.

13.CONCLUSION:

Corporate social responsibility is the key factor every business to sustain long in the competitive world. Compared to last couple of decades Corporate Social Responsibility activities are been gradually increased. Anticipation of business is something different and contribution of CSR is something different, in return company wants to earn profit. There should not be any middleman who makes profit in the adoption of Corporate Social Responsibility. The effect should be directly with the company and the society. Besides providing to development of society the CSR should be in favour of society. The challenges which the company has in the adoption of Corporate Social Responsibility it should be properly planned and converted into the favour of society. In certain extent company increase its Corporate Social Responsibility activities only if the profit increase continuously. It is clearly stated the development which the government did not done it is done through the adoption of Corporate Social Responsibility.

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